

Concepts of Maximal Greatness and the Nature of God Across Major Religious Traditions

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma¹

¹Email: drkrishnakantsharma@gmail.com; M: 9504782781;

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6009-3024>

Abstract:

This paper explores the concept of maximal greatness as perceived in major religious traditions, particularly focusing on theistic beliefs where a maximally great reality is equated with a maximally great person or God. We analyze varying conceptions of God's attributes, such as omnipotence, omniscience, and omnipresence, while highlighting theological debates, including God's impassibility in Western theism and the relationship between God and the space-time continuum in Indian theism. Additionally, the paper examines differing interpretations of God's nature across Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity, and the implications of these differences for understanding the divine. The study concludes by discussing the concept of limited deities and how these shape the broader religious experience.

Keywords: Concepts of God; Religion and God; Greatness and Nature of God.

The object of the attitudes valued in major religious traditions is often considered to be something of maximal greatness. While conceptions of maximal greatness differ, theists commonly believe that such a reality must be embodied by a maximally great person or God. Most theists agree that a maximally great person would possess attributes such as omnipresence, omnipotence, omniscience, and supreme goodness. However, there is disagreement about other attributes of God. This can be illustrated by examining debates in Western theism regarding God's impassibility and discussions in Indian theism about God's relationship to the space-time world. This exploration concludes with a look at some concepts of limited deities (Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, 2012).

Paul Tillich argued that the core of religious attitudes is an "ultimate concern," which he describes as "total." The object of ultimate concern is experienced as numinous or holy, distinct from ordinary and profane realities. It is also seen as overwhelmingly real and valuable—so much so that, in comparison, all other things appear empty and worthless. This ultimate concern demands total surrender and promises total fulfillment (Tillich, 1951).

Despite agreeing that a maximally great reality must be a transcendentally great person, theists often differ on what other attributes maximal greatness entails. While most theists believe God is omnipresent, omniscient, omnipotent, and all-good, they sometimes disagree on how these attributes should be understood. Other differences are more profound. For instance, there is debate over God's impassibility in Western theism and God's relationship to the space-time world in Indian theism.

Most theists agree with Ramanuja's description of God as the "supreme self" or person—omniscient, omnipotent, and all-good. However, classical Christian theists have also attributed four "metaphysical attributes" to God: simplicity, timelessness, immutability, and impassibility. The doctrine of simplicity holds that all of God's real or intrinsic properties are identical with each other and with His being or nature. Many classical Western theists also view God as timeless, existing entirely outside of time. God is also considered immutable, meaning His real properties cannot change—an idea that follows from God's simplicity. Finally, classical Western theists believe God is impassible, meaning that while God creates, sustains, and governs the world—which depends on Him for both its being and its qualities—nothing acts upon or causally affects God. The world is influenced by God, but God is unaffected by it.

In Indian philosophy, it is often assumed that the cause of a thing's existence must be a material substratum (a "material cause") that is shaped or formed into a particular being, such as an elephant or an atom of earth or water.

Seeking God and identifying with a religion are distinct experiences. However, many people mistakenly assume that someone who does not identify with a particular religion must be an atheist. This is an affront to both God and genuine atheism. Religions are human institutions that, at their best, help people experience and draw closer to God.

A true atheist is someone who believes that existence is a mere accident of chance and that life has no inherent purpose or meaning, apart from what humans ascribe to it. Such an atheist would hold that there is nothing intrinsically good or bad about any human action; from a cosmic perspective, a murderer and a humanitarian are equals.

Religions are systems of beliefs and practices designed to enhance the experience of faith. Sometimes they help individuals uncover deeper levels of meaning in their lives, and sometimes they are merely tools people use to justify pre-existing beliefs and behaviors. Religion can provide insight and a framework for making good choices in a complex world, but it can also serve as an excuse for hatred and greed. Generally, religions, like people, do a bit of both (Jeff, 2012).

Dan Barker, a well-known atheist, has been debating the existence of God for over two decades. One of his key assertions is that no one can coherently define God. Because, he claims, no one can define God, we should conclude there is a high probability that God does not exist (Butt, 2009).

The claim that God cannot be coherently defined is contentious. While God is often defined as a spirit, this does not prevent intelligent discussion of God's attributes, existence, and qualities. Most dictionaries provide a working definition that is widely understandable. God is often described as the uncaused, all-powerful, all-knowing, merciful, gracious, eternal Spirit whose personality and attributes are manifest in religious texts such as the Bible. The notion that God cannot be defined is seen by some as a rhetorical tactic based on an unfounded materialistic philosophy. In truth, God can be clearly defined and differentiated from all other entities to such an extent that debates like those between Barker and his opponents are possible and meaningful (Butt, 2009).

The Hindu religion is rooted in a sound philosophical tradition that evolved from the Vedic to the post-Vedic period, and from the Upanishads to the Puranas. The socialization of the Puranas and Buddhism differed from the Vedic approach, which emphasized both spiritual attainment and the welfare of the people, without room for misconceptions, deception, or personal gain. However, after the decline of Vedic civilization, new waves of socialization emerged, such as Buddhism and the Puranic traditions. These new forms often included idol worship, temple construction, and the worship of multiple gods. Many mythological stories seemed absurd, and the pure Vedic philosophy and six orthodox philosophies were largely ignored in favor of new ideas and practices. Myths and stories were created for religious socialization, but this often led to blind faith and the rise of pseudo-sciences like astrology. Temples became sources of personal income, with little oversight or regulation. In Hinduism, there is a distinction between Akshar (the indestructible), Devta (deities), and Bhagwan (incarnations of the supreme). Concepts like incarnation are debated among scholars, with some rejecting the notion that a supreme being would need to incarnate.

The concept of God in Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity varies, reflecting the distinct theological frameworks, cultural contexts, and spiritual understandings within each religion. Here is an overview of the concept of God in these three major world religions:

1. Hinduism

Hinduism is a complex and diverse religion with a wide range of beliefs about God. The concept of God in Hinduism can vary greatly depending on the specific tradition or philosophical school. However, some common themes include... (further elaboration would continue based on the original text).

- **Polytheism and Monotheism:** Hinduism encompasses both polytheistic and monotheistic beliefs. There are many deities in Hinduism, each representing different aspects of life and the cosmos. Major deities include Brahma (the creator), Vishnu (the preserver), and Shiva (the destroyer). These deities are worshiped in various forms and avatars (incarnations), such as Krishna and Rama, who are avatars of Vishnu.

- **Brahman:** At the highest level, Hinduism speaks of a single, ultimate reality known as **Brahman**. Brahman is the unchanging, infinite, immanent, and transcendent reality that is the Divine Ground of all beings. It is beyond personal gods and goddesses, beyond form and formlessness, and is the source of all existence. While many Hindus worship a particular deity, they often understand that all deities are manifestations of the one supreme Brahman.
- **Atman:** Closely related to the concept of Brahman is the idea of **Atman**, which is the individual soul or self. Hindu philosophy teaches that the Atman is ultimately identical to Brahman, suggesting a deep interconnectedness between the self and the divine.
- **Pantheism and Panentheism:** Hinduism can also be considered pantheistic (God is in everything) and panentheistic (everything is in God). The Divine is seen as present in all aspects of the universe, which is why many Hindus worship rivers, mountains, animals, and other natural elements as sacred.
- **Personal and Impersonal Aspects of God:** In Hinduism, God can be both personal and impersonal. Personal forms of God include deities like Krishna and Shiva, who are worshiped with prayers, rituals, and festivals. Impersonal aspects refer to the abstract, formless Brahman.

2. Islam

Islam is a strictly monotheistic religion, centered around the belief in a single, all-powerful God known as **Allah**. The concept of God in Islam is characterized by several key attributes:

- **Tawhid (Oneness of God):** The central tenet of Islam is the absolute oneness and uniqueness of God. **Tawhid** emphasizes that there is only one God, who is singular, indivisible, and incomparable. This belief rejects any form of polytheism, idolatry, or association of partners with God.
- **Attributes of God:** Islamic theology describes God as having numerous attributes, such as being omniscient (all-knowing), omnipotent (all-powerful), omnipresent (present everywhere), merciful, just, compassionate, and eternal. These attributes are outlined in the Qur'an, Islam's holy scripture, and are fundamental to understanding God's nature.
- **Transcendence and Immanence:** God in Islam is both transcendent (beyond all that exists, beyond comprehension) and immanent (closer to the believers than their jugular vein). God is involved in the world but is not part of the creation itself; rather, God is distinct and wholly other.
- **No Physical Form or Image:** In Islam, God is considered beyond any physical form or human conception. Any attempt to depict God in physical form is seen as a grave sin (Shirk) because it compromises the unique oneness of God. Therefore, Islamic art avoids representations of God or any prophets, focusing instead on calligraphy and geometric patterns.
- **Revelation through Prophets:** Muslims believe that God has revealed His will to humanity through a series of prophets, including Adam, Noah, Abraham, Moses, Jesus, and finally, Muhammad, who is considered the last prophet. The Qur'an is regarded as the literal word of God, revealed to Muhammad.

3. Christianity

Christianity is a monotheistic religion, but its understanding of God is defined by the doctrine of the **Trinity**. Key concepts of God in Christianity include:

- **The Trinity:** The central doctrine in most Christian denominations is the belief in the **Trinity**, which defines God as one being in three distinct persons: **God the Father**, **God the Son (Jesus Christ)**, and **God the Holy Spirit**. This doctrine holds that while God is one in essence, God's three persons are co-equal, co-eternal, and consubstantial (of the same substance).
 - **God the Father:** Seen as the creator and sustainer of the universe, embodying qualities like omnipotence, omniscience, and omnipresence.
 - **God the Son (Jesus Christ):** Believed to be both fully divine and fully human. Christians believe Jesus is the incarnate Word of God who came to Earth to redeem humanity from sin through his life, death, and resurrection.
 - **God the Holy Spirit:** Considered the presence of God in the world and within believers, providing guidance, comfort, and spiritual gifts.

- **Personal and Loving God:** Christianity emphasizes a personal relationship with God, who is seen as loving, merciful, and actively involved in the lives of believers. God is approached as a loving Father who desires a relationship with His creation.
- **Revelation and Scripture:** Christians believe that God has revealed Himself through the Bible, particularly through the life and teachings of Jesus Christ. The Bible is considered the inspired word of God, and Jesus is seen as the ultimate revelation of God's nature and will.
- **Salvation and Redemption:** Central to Christian belief is the idea that God offers salvation and redemption to humanity through Jesus Christ. This salvation is seen as a gift of grace, not earned by human efforts but granted through faith in Jesus Christ's sacrificial death and resurrection.

Comparison and Contrast

- **Monotheism:** All three religions are monotheistic, but their understanding of the oneness of God varies. Islam and Christianity are strictly monotheistic, but Christianity's concept of the Trinity introduces a complex unity. Hinduism, while encompassing monotheistic beliefs (Brahman), also allows for a diversity of gods and forms of worship.
- **Nature of God:** In Islam and Christianity, God is a personal being with whom believers can have a relationship. In Hinduism, God can be both a personal deity (like Krishna or Shiva) and an impersonal absolute (Brahman).
- **Role of Scriptures:** All three religions have foundational texts: the **Vedas** and other scriptures in Hinduism, the **Qur'an** in Islam, and the **Bible** in Christianity. These texts define the nature of God and guide the religious practices and beliefs of adherents.
- **Idolatry:** Islam strictly forbids any depiction of God and considers idolatry a grave sin. Christianity also generally prohibits the worship of images, though there is a tradition of religious iconography, particularly in Catholic and Orthodox branches. Hinduism, on the other hand, uses images and idols as representations of the divine, believing that God can be worshiped in many forms.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the conception of God as a maximally great being varies significantly across different religious traditions. While theists broadly agree on certain attributes such as omniscience, omnipotence, and omnipresence, the interpretation of these attributes, along with others like impassibility and the nature of God's interaction with the world, remains a topic of debate. These variations are further emphasized in the contrasting theological frameworks of Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity, where the nature and attributes of God are shaped by distinct religious and cultural contexts. Understanding these differences is crucial in appreciating the diversity of religious thought and the complex nature of divine concepts across global religions.

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